

Discrete Quantum Energy Levels and Average Velocity?

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An important feature of bound state quantum mechanics is their discrete energy levels, unlike those of classical bound states which are continuous. This follows from the mathematics of the solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation and boundary conditions. In other words, it seems physical arguments are not usually made to account for the discrete nature of quantum energy levels. In this note, we try to argue that bound state quantum mechanical wavefunctions usually have humps and it seems that a whole number of complete humps need to fit into the bound region. This in turn leads to discrete energy levels, as other energies correspond to partial humps being included. A hump is characterized by two zero points of the wavefunction. If complete humps exist at the outer boundaries of a quantum solution, the wavefunction and spatial density are both zero (or drop rapidly) at the outer points of a hump, something well-known. In this note, we argue that density averages of various functions of momentum i.e. $W^*(x)W(x) \sum_p f(p) P(p/x)$ are physical observables. In particular, the density average of $\langle p \rangle$ is important as it describes averages momentum flow (comprised of both forward and backward moving $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ terms). $\langle pp \rangle$, on the other hand, leads to a p rms which is identical to classical momentum and is automatically zero at turning points while $\langle p \rangle$ is not.

We argue that to have a bound state, there should be no momentum flow at outer boundary points which forces the density to either have zeros or approach zero in order to force the density average of $\langle p \rangle$ i.e. $W^*W \sum_p p P(p/x)$ to be zero. (Alternatively, $\langle p \rangle$ could be zero, but this leads to peak density with no flow which is unusual.) Quantum bound states are usually based on a hump structure, so complete humps must be included in any solution to ensure a dropping or zero wavefunction at the boundary. This automatically restricts the number of solutions to a discrete set i.e. discrete energies.

Classical versus Quantum Velocities

A classical bound state satisfies $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ with $v(x)=\text{velocity}=0$ at the turning points. Quantum bound states also satisfy a conservation of energy equation:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1)) \quad W(x)=\text{wavefunction}$$

The first term is KE ave(x) from which one may obtain $p_{rms}(x) = mv(x)$ classical. Thus, there is an rms momentum in quantum mechanics which matches classical momentum exactly. The issue is that there is also a second momentum:

$$-i\hbar/dx W / W = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p a(p)\exp(ipx)]/W(x) \quad ((2))$$

This average momentum is critical in determining the shape of the wavefunction as:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i (-i \ln(W) / dx)) \quad ((3))$$

In particular, $\langle p \rangle$ determines the hump structure of quantum bound wavefunctions.

$\text{Sqrt}[\langle p \rangle] = mv(x)$ has zeros at the classical turning points, but $\langle p \rangle$ does not. This leads to the problem of momentum flow (in both directions) at the classical turning points in quantum mechanics. Even if $\langle p \rangle$ has a certain overall sign leading toward interior motion at the turning points, it is comprised of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ terms and so there should be motion outside of the interior region (bound region) defined by the turning points. This, however, suggests that one does not have a bound state, because a bound system should be essentially localized even in quantum mechanics. Thus, one should have a zero or increasingly small value of density times $\langle p \rangle$ motion at the boundaries of the quantum bound state.

The Role of Humps in Quantum Bound States

As discussed in the previous section, $W(x)\langle p \rangle$ should approach zero at the “endpoints” of the bound quantum system and these points should be similar to the classical turning points. Thus, even if the quantum region stretches from -infinite to infinite as in an oscillator problem, the overwhelming amount density is within the classical turning points. $\langle p \rangle$ is not zero at the classical turning points, so this suggests the wavefunction $W(x)$ should drop very rapidly near these points. One may argue that in order to have density(x) $\langle p \rangle$ drop to zero, either the wavefunction or $\langle p \rangle$ may drop to zero. In general, the wavefunction peaks at points for which $\langle p \rangle$ is zero. Thus, if one chooses to have $\langle p \rangle$ zero, this represents a peak of density i.e. the top of a hump which may be quite a distance from the bottom of the hump. Thus, one would have a large amount of density with no velocity which would be unusual. Thus, it seems more likely to have $W(x)$ approach zero at the outer points of the bound state.

The requirement that $W(x)$ be zero or drop rapidly at the outer ends of the bound quantum region suggests that not every energy E leads to a quantum bound state. Only energies which represent whole numbers of humps within the bound region may be used. Energies leading to partial humps at the endpoints do not lead to equilibrium solutions. In other words, there are discrete energy levels

Two Examples,

The first example is that of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. The wavefunction $C \sin(\text{pave } x)$ is zero at the endpoints, thus leading to the zero density described above. $\langle p \rangle$ is $\text{pave } \cos(\text{pave } x) / \sin(\text{pave } x)$ so even after multiplying by density, the term $\cos(\text{pave } x)$ peaks at $x=0$. Thus, a zero density is needed to bring the product $\langle p \rangle$ density to zero at the endpoint. If one weakens the infinite potential at the wall, i.e. replaces it with a finite potential, the density is no longer zero at $x=0$, but drops rapidly from whatever fixed value it may have at $x=0$, in keeping with the ideas discussed in the above section.

The second example is that of an oscillator. The ground state consists of a Gaussian wavefunction i.e. a single hump. Higher energy solutions consist of extra humps with the discrete energy $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ allowing for a whole number of humps to appear so that the

boundary humps may drop to zero as they are multiplied by $\exp(-ax)$. Thus, only certain energies yield a set of full humps with a falloff of $\exp(-ax)$. The discrete set of solutions follow from the time-independent Schrodinger equation together with the condition that the solution drops to 0 at \pm infinite. In this note, we argue this is linked to density $\langle p \rangle$ dropping to zero at the endpoints of the bound region. In fact, one may calculate classical turning points and see that they fall within the region of the dropping quantum spatial density.

Conclusion

Usually, discrete energy levels are explained by imposing boundary conditions on solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In this note, we investigate a physical reason, namely that $\text{density}(x)\langle p \rangle$ must drop to zero at the rough points bounding the quantum bound region. $\sqrt{\langle pp \rangle}$ i.e. p rms equals the classical momentum and so is already zero at the classical turning points, while $\langle p \rangle$ is not. We argue that setting $\text{density}\langle x \rangle = 0$ or allowing it to rapidly approach 0 allows for this goal to be achieved. As quantum bound solutions are usually comprised of humps, we argue that each subsequent solution contains an extra full hump. This leads to the idea of discrete energy because only certain energies allow for a full hump to be added to a previous energy solution. The full hump allows for the outer hump region to drop to zero. We consider two examples, that of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls and the oscillator.